

Job Crafting Effect: Examine Self-Efficacy and Competence on Work Engagement

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: June 20, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: January 25, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Student Motivation, Student Engagement, Self-Regulation, Learning Achievement</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5902800</p>	<p><i>This study aims to examine the effect of self-efficacy and competence on job crafting and work engagement. Previous research has not explored the influence and important role of job crafting in influencing work engagement in vocational-based schools. The delegation of learning to teachers during the pandemic, which is carried out online, needs support. Job crafting makes teachers improvise, adapt, innovate, and create a creation following learning objectives. This study has 177 vocational-based school teacher respondents, namely shipping in Indonesia. The results show that self-efficacy has an indirect effect on work engagement mediated by job crafting. This study also proves that competence, directly and indirectly, affects work engagement mediated by job crafting. This research implies that teachers need to be given adequate authority to create innovation and creativity and have strong ties to the organization. The results of this study can be used as a guide in determining school policies</i></p>

Introduction

In a school, the ability of teachers to believe in their competence is important because if the teacher can believe that the competencies possessed can be utilized in the learning process, it encourages the emergence of a belief to take action. This process is part of self-efficacy, where teachers are required to be confident in carrying out the processes and tasks to carry out learning in the classroom. The process goes through several stages so that there are teachers who are confident in carrying out their duties, although, on the other hand, there are teachers who are not sure about carrying out their duties. Teachers need to understand the tasks that must be done so that the process provides an impetus to identify the tasks that must be done in the learning process. Previous research has proven that self-efficacy can encourage good task execution, so that self-efficacy can make a job fit for purpose[1]. In addition, self-efficacy needs to be encouraged by competency; if the teacher has good competence, it can help in carrying out the task. The implementation of the teacher's duties does not only carry out the learning process in the classroom. However, other processes can be an innovation in the learning section, such as online learning media, especially in the current pandemic situation and conditions that encourage demands to do work online. Teachers must ensure that responsible students can understand the material and acquire cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects[2].

The challenge that arises is that vocational education is a process to educate students; most of them get education by prioritizing practice in the field, such as shipping schools. In the marine school education process, which is oriented towards the ability of students to understand all aspects of the ship. Teachers need support who can adapt their work online, even though the pandemic hit; however, the learning process is expected to be like when learning is carried out face-to-face, so that the learning process can present the same space of knowledge and student competencies. Every student who graduates from marine school is required to understand the ship according to their respective educational competencies. The challenge of vocational education is not easy because the online learning process requires an infrastructure support to really be able to provide knowledge and emphasize psychomotor aspects more dominantly. In online learning, teachers are required to be able to adapt their work. Previous research has shown the ability of teachers to identify and re-implement work with creativity supported by the ability to create a job or innovation and creativity called job crafting, which will encourage work engagement[3]. This study aims to identify and examine self-efficacy and competence on job crafting and their effect on work engagement.

Literature Review

Job crafting is a behavior change process carried out by employees to adjust the job characteristics, either physically or cognitively, according to the preferences, skills, and needs of the employees themselves so that the work done becomes more meaningful[3]. Job crafting is the behavior of employees in balancing the demands of

work with preferences, skills, and needs in producing changes in the number of tasks and workload perspectives[4]. When an employee succeeds in creating a work environment characterized by job resources and challenging job demands. Job crafting can be interpreted as an employee skill that can redesign their work on their initiative without management involvement. The work carried out by employees feels easier and more comfortable because there is a balance between job demands and resources with personal abilities or employee needs[5].

Hypothesis development

The effect of self-efficacy on job crafting and work engagement

Self-efficacy is a belief that arises from a person feeling capable of doing an action. In the context of this study, a teacher who has self-efficacy is a teacher who has confidence in carrying out his duties. The task of a teacher at a vocational-based school is to convey material and improve students' competence to be able to master technical matters following their respective fields. The teacher's ability to believe in action will encourage an innovation adapted to his work to convey material and improve student competence to master technical skills after attending learning[6]. In the context of online learning due to the corona pandemic, efforts to improve competence and technical skills become a challenge for teachers because the online learning process is not carried out face-to-face, so there needs to be creativity, innovation, and adjustments and adaptations from teachers to be able to increase student competence. The challenge is when the teacher is not able to provide practical explanations directly. Direct practice will provide better abilities compared to the online learning process with vocational education, so that previous research states that self-efficacy affects job crafting. The teacher's belief in taking action will encourage the creation of innovation in the learning process that is tailored to each teacher's ability[7]. The process of student competence goes through various stages to carry out an action that is deemed appropriate to the technical competence and does not forget the obligations to be able to encourage cognitive and affective aspects.

Self-efficacy will affect work engagement because someone who believes in action and feels able to carry out the work will encourage someone to survive in an organization. The ability to survive in the organization is a good step so that human resources, especially in education, can do their jobs comfortably because work engagement is a reflection of comfort in carrying out work. When someone is comfortable, there will be a sense of belonging to the organization, namely the school, their home base[8]. The job as a teacher is to educate students to master their technical skills in the field of vocational self-efficacy and be able to encourage them to take certain actions so that the attachment to the organization becomes greater. Suppose someone can encourage the creation of a strong emotional bond to the organization so that apart from being driven by the belief that work engagement can be encouraged through job crafting. The work can be done following innovation and creativity, and the teacher can be given a responsibility that can be managed independently, bringing comfort at work. Work comfort is a reflection of work engagement. The teacher feels at home and comfortable in work so that work engagement, namely in providing the education and learning process, feels comfortable and has an emotional bond[9].

H1: The stronger self-efficacy encourages the creation of job crafting for shipping school teachers

H2: Job crafting forms work engagement for shipping school teachers

H3: Job crafting mediates the effect of self-efficacy on work engagement on shipping school teachers

The influence of competence on job crafting and work engagement

Competence is the ability to act. In the context of this research, competence is the ability of the teacher to convey material and form the technical competence of students to understand well aspects of shipping that are following their field. The context of competence is a process in learning so that teachers are required to convey material that students can understand without leaving any aspects of technical competence that must be mastered during a pandemic. The learning process is carried out online so that the implementation of learning needs to get serious attention and requires innovation and adaptation. In vocational education that emphasizes more on practice, the approach by prioritizing the psychomotor aspect needs to get a greater emphasis so that the psychomotor aspect has an important influence in mastering technical competence, especially in the shipping sector. When learning is over, students can obtain material and apply their technical abilities in the shipping field. Online learning is a challenge in itself. Teachers are required to maintain the quality of their learning by prioritizing aspects of technical competence through online learning. The teacher's authority and responsibility in carrying out his work are stated in job crafting. The teacher has the authority to adopt, and the ability to complete his work can be adjusted to the style of each individual. Previous research encourages research on competence and its effect on job crafting. If the teacher understands the material and what it means to have a competency, it will be easy to adapt and innovate so that the crafting job can be done in the online learning process. The division of authority can create an increase in students' abilities in the field of shipping technical competence following learning objectives

A teacher needs to have technical competence in creating innovations in the learning process. When the teacher is comfortable in his work, it can create work engagement[10], meaning that the teacher is comfortable in doing

his job because he already has the competence, so that it can create a feeling of emotional ties to the organizations that are the shelter for the teacher in carrying out their learning, the organization in question is the school. When the teacher feels comfortable doing his job because he has certain competencies that can be applied in the learning process, it can encourage better work engagement. Work engagement is a reflection of comfort in an organization so that, as stated, comfort at work will create an emotional bond. Emotional ties can be formed because of a competency possessed by someone who follows his competence, feels happy, and has an emotional bond. Previous research states that there is an influence of competence on work engagement. Previous research has shown that there is an influence of competence on the job crafting. Job crafting is an effort to manage responsibilities according to the creativity and innovation of teachers, so that Crafting can bring up a process and creative ideas but does not leave obligations in the learning process. Teachers must bring up affective, cognitive, and psychomotor abilities, especially the emphasis on psychomotor aspects in vocational-based schools, namely shipping schools.

H4: Competence has a positive effect on job crafting

H5: Job crafting forms work engagement for shipping school teachers

H6: Job crafting mediates the effect of competence on work engagement in shipping school teachers

Method

This study has four variables, namely self-efficacy, competence, job crafting, and work engagement. The four variables are adaptations adapted to the research location, namely the shipping school to form graduates who understand the aspects of shipping optimally. The process to obtain respondents is to send a questionnaire that the teacher can fill out so that the researcher can collect it even though the location of the teacher or school is scattered. The questionnaire can be easily collected; the data collection process is carried out using an online questionnaire that can be filled out at any time; after the questionnaire is filled in, it is processed using statistical tests through the AMOS application.

Result

Validity and Reliability

Based on Table 1 and Table 2, validity and reliability test result are represented.

Table 1. Validity Test Result

Variable	Indicator	Pearson Correlation	Mean	S.D
Self-Efficacy	SE1	0.872	4.4011	0.65937
	SE2	0.908	4.2090	0.65395
	SE3	0.897	4.2090	0.67951
Competence	C1	0.784	4.1582	0.72914
	C2	0.865	4.1582	0.61962
	C3	0.844	4.1977	0.60340
Job-Crafting	JC1	0.816	4.2599	0.62179
	JC2	0.845	4.3503	0.62287
	JC3	0.842	4.3107	0.65674
Work Engagement	WE1	0.853	4.2881	0.63203
	WE2	0.883	4.3672	0.64460
	WE3	0.799	4.3164	0.58525

Table 2. Reliability Test Result

Variable	Cronbach Alpha
Self-Efficacy	0.872
Competence	0.766
Job-Crafting	0.781
Work Engagement	0.801

Table 3. Regression Analysis Result

Variable	Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Self Efficacy -> Job Crafting	,522	,103	5,072	***
Competence -> Job Crafting	,306	,109	2,798	,005

Job Crafting -> Work Engagement	,482	,238	2,029	,042
Self Efficacy ->Work Engagement	,175	,161	1,087	,277
Competence ->Work Engagement	,262	,131	1,994	,046

Figure 1. Research Framework

Discussion

The results of this study indicate that self-efficacy has a positive and significant effect on job crafting, meaning that teachers who believe in carrying out the online learning process can adapt so that their work can be carried out optimally. The teacher's belief can encourage a creative innovation process that can be used in the online learning process in vocational education that prioritizes practice, meaning that technical competencies need to be deepened and mastered by students. Teachers can create an innovative process in the online learning process. The online process is driven by technical support, such as a learning management system that can allow teachers to explore the menus in the application. Teachers can provide innovation in the learning process such as videos, audio, pictures, and other instructions that are deemed capable of encouraging students' technical competence [3]. Videos and instructions from teachers can create a learning process that is adaptive to situations and conditions during a pandemic, namely the online learning process; students can follow the learning process through the learning management system available through schools. The learning process is related to teacher self-efficacy, the belief that the teacher can be encouraged and implemented in job crafting so that innovation and creativity can be carried out optimally. The existence of this creativity can increase comfort in the learning process because it is not done in a monotonous manner so that students can understand the material well and teachers can do their jobs according to their respective responsibilities.

The results of this study indicate that self-efficacy does not directly affect work engagement. Still, the results of job crafting research mediate the effect of self-efficacy on work engagement in full [11]. It means that the crafting job must be formed first before creating work engagement on teacher efficacy. This study proves that teachers need to have job crafting, meaning that responsibilities adapted to adaptive innovation and creativity for teachers will bring comfort in the learning process. This research can present evidence that adaptation and responsibility given to teachers need a climate that encourages the freedom of teachers to create learning processes following their respective innovations and creativity. Teachers are given full and absolute responsibility to carry out the learning process, however unable to separate from the corridor to ensure that the learning process is of high quality. When the teacher gains creativity and freedom in the learning process, it will encourage comfort in working. The teacher does not get strong pressure. However, there is freedom that can create comfort in learning. Comfort in learning encourages comfort in work which is a reflection of work engagement [12].

Competence directly affects job crafting, meaning that it indicates that the teacher's ability to understand the material that will be given to students will provide opportunities to innovate creativity and learning media that can be applied in the learning process. What students should have, teacher competence is the key to improving students' abilities. Especially to understand cognitive aspects, affective and psychomotor are the main aspects of

vocational-based schools' learning process. Understanding through videos or pictures can show the reality in the field so that students understand well what is learned in vocational schools, not just stopping at the cognitive aspects g contains knowledge but needs to be deeper in the application of the knowledge[13].The output that students can apply and own is the ability to take action in the field in the context of this research at the Marine School, where students can practice directly on the ship.

Competence is a key aspect and directly affects work engagement. When teachers as human resources in schools will have the competence and have an emotional bond with the organization, it will be beneficial. Competence has an important role in creating emotional bonds, meaning that work engagement can be created through a process and security at work. The desire to teach and this ability is a tacit knowledge of the teacher's ability to create an effective, efficient, and fun learning process by prioritizing the psychomotor aspects that need to be mastered by students so that it can encourage engagement in an organization[14]. This research proves that job crafting partially mediates competence's effect on work engagement, which means that rating can be a key that makes work engagement meaningful.

Conclusion

This study indicates that self-efficacy has an indirect effect on work engagement but is mediated by job crafting. This study proves that job crafting fully mediates the effect of self-efficacy on work engagement. The results show that job crafting partially mediates the effect of competence on work engagement. a proof that the convenience of teachers to have the authority of authority and innovation in the learning process can encourage stronger emotional ties to the organization of teachers with their authority to provide the learning process to students in their way by referring to the technical competencies that must be achieved, especially in the cognitive-affective aspect and psychomotor so that the freedom and authority will make the learning process more enjoyable besides the teacher being more comfortable working in the organization armed with efficacy self and competence.

Suggestion

Subsequent research can explore the implications that arise after it is proven that work engagement is influenced by job crafting and self-efficacy. Work engagement competence is one of the key variables to determine job satisfaction and teacher performance.In the future so that further research can explore the consequences of these variables. This research can be used as a reference in determining school policies to provide flexibility to teachers in carrying out the learning process in their respective ways but still guided by the output expected by the subjects concerned.

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